

26	S5 AU tests	31
27	S6 Filtering out distant outgroups helps reduce long branch attraction	37
28		
29	S7 Results for another Metazoa dataset	39
30	S8 Compositional heterogeneity across sequences	40
31	S9 Convergence measures of Phylobayes analyses	43

32 S1 COMMANDS TO RUN THE CAT-PMSF PIPELINE

33 Figure 1 shows the required steps to apply the CAT-PMSF pipeline on a phylo-
 34 genetic dataset. Although other implementations exist and may be used for the
 35 various steps, our analyses were conducted solely using IQ-TREE 2 (Minh et al.,
 36 2020) and PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004). Step 1 can be done via IQ-
 37 TREE 2 (Minh et al., 2020) on an alignment preferably in PHYLIP (Felsenstein,
 38 1989) format, because Phylobayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) expects that as
 39 input type in Step 2.

```
1 iqtree2 -s alignment.phylip -m LG+F+G4
```

40 This will output a maximum likelihood (ML) tree file called `alignment.phylip.treefile`.
 41 Step 2 uses PhyloBayes MPI (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004). Before running Step
 42 2, benchmarks can be performed to choose the best number of parallel tasks the
 43 MPI program should use.

```
1 mpirun -np 48 pb_mpi -cat -gtr -d alignment.phylip -T alignment.phylip.treefile  
  ↪ cat_gtr_alignment_chain1  
2 mpirun -np 48 pb_mpi -cat -gtr -d alignment.phylip -T alignment.phylip.treefile  
  ↪ cat_gtr_alignment_chain2
```

44 To assess convergence of the two chains, the guidelines for *acceptable* runs as
 45 stated in the PhyloBayes MPI documentation ([https://github.com/bayesiancook/
 46 pbmpi/blob/master/pb_mpiManual1.8.pdf](https://github.com/bayesiancook/pbmpi/blob/master/pb_mpiManual1.8.pdf)) are used. That is, the entries of the
 47 `tracecomp` command should have effective sample sizes above 50 and relative dif-
 48 ferences below 0.3.

```
1 # Phylobayes MPI 1.8 or Phylobayes 4.1c  
2 tracecomp -x 1000 1 cat_gtr_alignment_chain1 cat_gtr_alignment_chain2  
3 # prior to Phylobayes MPI 1.8 or prior Phylobayes 4.1c the burnin argument may only  
  ↪ support one value  
4 tracecomp -x 1000 cat_gtr_alignment_chain1 cat_gtr_alignment_chain2
```

49 The `-x` switch defines the number of burn-in iterations (1000) and the sampling

50 frequency (1).

51 An example output for a successful run for the Nematoda dataset with model
52 CAT+GTR+G4 is shown below.

```
1 # tracecomp -x 1000 gtr_nematode_icc_chain1 gtr_nematode_icc_chain2
2   name           effsize      rel_diff
3   loglik         540           0.15339
4   length        5339           0.250924
5   alpha         4724           0.182099
6   Nmode         1292           0.0321017
7   statent       301           0.00237055
8   statalpha     419           0.180082
9   rrent         342           0.130712
10  rrmean        6179           0.00141907
```

53 To export the site-specific stationary distributions from a converged PhyloBayes
54 MPI run, one can use the `readpb_mpi` utility.

```
1 readpb_mpi -ss -x 1000 1 cat_gtr_alignment_chain1
```

55 This command will produce the file `cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.siteprofiles`.

56 In case PhyloBayes was run with GTR exchangeabilities, the inferred exchange-
57 ability matrix also has to be exported and supplied in Step 3 of the CAT-PMSF
58 pipeline:

```
1 readpb_mpi -rr -x 1000 1 cat_gtr_alignment_chain1
```

59 The output file is `cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.meanrr`.

60 The custom script converting outputs of PhyloBayes MPI to IQ-TREE 2 com-
61 patible formats can be found in the GitHub repository in the Dryad Digital Reposi-
62 tory: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g79cnp5rh> and at <https://github.com/drenal/cat-pmsf-paper>. The usage is as follows:
63

```
1 python3 convert_site-dists_v2.py cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.siteprofiles
```

64 This will produce `cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.sitefreq`.

65 Similarly a script is provided in the GitHub repository in the Dryad Digital
66 Repository: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g79cnp5rh> and at <https://github.com/drenal/cat-pmsf-paper> which converts the exchangeabilities:
67

```
1 python3 convert-exchangeabilities.py cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.meanrr
```

68 This will create `cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.exchangeabilities`

69 Step 3 of the CAT-PMSF pipeline consists of supplying IQ-TREE 2 (Minh
70 et al., 2020) the posterior mean site-specific stationary distributions of amino acids
71 (and the posterior mean exchangeabilities in case of the GTR model), and running
72 IQ-TREE 2 on the alignment:

```
1 # for custom exchangeabilities:  
2 iqtrees2 -s alignment.phylip -m cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.exchangeabilities+G4 -fs  
  ↪ cat_gtr_alignment_chain1.sitefreq --prefix alignment.phylip.gtrcatpmsf  
3 # for predefined exchangeabilities, e.g. LG:  
4 iqtrees2 -s alignment.phylip -m LG+G4 -fs cat_lg_alignment_chain1.sitefreq --prefix  
  ↪ alignment.phylip.lgcatpmsf
```

73 This will produce the `alignment.phylip.gtrcatpmsf.treefile` or `alignment.phylip.lgcatpmsf.treefile`
74 ML tree inferred using the specified custom model.

76 The insets of Figures 3 and 4 show reduced topologies. In this section, we provide
77 the complete ML trees of the datasets inferred by the CAT-PMSF method at Step
78 3 and the site-homogeneous method at Step 1. Due to the high variance of the
79 branch lengths, we provide the topology with the real branch length denoted in
80 labels above the branches. Red dots at the nodes of the trees signal differences
81 between the topology inferred in Step 1 and 3 of the CAT-PMSF pipeline and
82 correspond to the Robinson-Foulds metric (Robinson and Foulds, 1981). The full
83 trees for Philippe et al.'s Nematoda and Platyhelminthes and Nematoda datasets
84 in Figures S1 and S2 respectively, the full trees for Brinkmann et al.'s Microsporidia
85 dataset are in Figure S3. The full trees for Simion et al.'s Metazoa dataset are in
86 Figures S5 and S4, and the full trees of the other Metazoa dataset from Ryan et al.
87 are in Figure S6.

Figure S1: **Detailed trees for Philippe et al.'s Platyhelminthes dataset.** Maximum likelihood topologies inferred by the site-heterogeneous GTR+CAT-PMSF model (a), and the site-homogeneous LG model (b) of the Philippe et al. (2005) Platyhelminthes dataset representing 32 species. Color codes are the same for species of the same taxa. Red dots mark differences between topologies (a) and (b) and correspond to the Robinson-Foulds metric (Robinson and Foulds, 1981). Values above branches represent inferred branch lengths, values below the branches represent bootstrap support. On the inset topology in Figure 3a, Chordata include Echinodermata; and Chytridiomycota, Glomeromycota, Basidiomycota and Ascomycota form Fungi.

(a) ML tree of Step 3

(b) ML tree of Step 1

Figure S2: **Detailed trees for Philippe et al.'s Nematoda dataset.** Maximum likelihood topologies inferred by the site-heterogeneous GTR+CAT-PMSF model (a), and the site-homogeneous LG model (b) of the Philippe et al. (2005) Nematoda dataset representing 37 species. Color codes are the same for species of the same taxa. Red dots mark the differences between topologies (a) and (b) and correspond to the Robinson-Foulds metric (Robinson and Foulds, 1981). Values above branches represent inferred branch lengths, values below branches represent bootstrap support. On the inset topology in Figure 3b, Chordata include Echinodermata; and Chytridiomycota, Glomeromycota, Basidiomycota and Ascomycota form Fungi.

Figure S3: **Detailed trees for the Brinkmann et al. dataset.** Maximum likelihood topologies inferred by the site-heterogeneous GTR+CAT-PMSF model (a), and the site-homogeneous LG model (b) of the Brinkmann et al. (2005) dataset representing 40 species. Color codes are the same for species of the same taxa. Red dots mark differences between topologies (a) and (b) and correspond to the Robinson-Foulds metric (Robinson and Foulds, 1981). Values above branches represent inferred branch lengths, values below branches represent bootstrap support. The inset topology in Figure 3c collects the phyla Apicomplexa, Ciliphora, Oomycota, Heterokonta and Ochrophyta under the supergroup TSAR; whereas there is no distinction between Planatea, Chlorophyta and Rhodophyta. Ascomycota, Basidiomycota, Glomeromycota and Chytridiomycotina form the Fungi group.

(a) ML tree of Step 3

(b) ML tree of Step 1

Figure S4: **Detailed trees for Simion et al.’s reduced dataset.** Maximum likelihood topologies inferred by the site-heterogeneous GTR+CAT-PMSF model (a), and the site-homogeneous LG model (b) of the reduced Simion et al. (2017) dataset representing 90 species. Color codes are the same for species of the same taxa. Red dots mark the differences between trees (a) and (b) and correspond to the Robinson-Foulds metric (Robinson and Foulds, 1981). Values above branches represent inferred branch lengths, values below branches represent bootstrap support.

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Figure S5: **Detailed trees for Simion et al.’s full dataset.** Maximum likelihood topologies inferred by the site-heterogeneous GTR+CAT-PMSF model (a), and the site-homogeneous LG model (b) of the Simion et al. (2017) dataset representing 97 species. Color codes are the same for species of the same taxa. Red dots mark differences between topologies (a) and (b) and correspond to the Robinson-Foulds metric (Robinson and Foulds, 1981). Values above branches represent inferred branch lengths, values below branches represent bootstrap support.

Figure S6: **Detailed trees for the Ryan et al. dataset.** Maximum likelihood topologies inferred by the site-heterogeneous GTR+CAT-PMSF model (a), and the site-homogeneous LG model (b) of the Ryan et al. (2013) dataset representing 60 species. Color codes are the same for species of the same taxa. Red dots mark differences between topologies (a) and (b) and correspond to the Robinson-Foulds metric (Robinson and Foulds, 1981). Values above branches represent inferred branch lengths, values below branches represent bootstrap support.

88 S3 MODEL PERFORMANCE

89 In this section, we present extended results with more models for all analyses
 90 performed in this work including a new way of visualizing the support between
 91 two competing topologies over the spectrum of sites with different K_{eff} . In the
 92 following, we briefly describe additional methods necessary to create these figures.

93 *K_{eff} cumulative log-likelihood difference figures.* – Figures S8, S9, and S10 show
 94 cumulative log-likelihood differences. The cumulative log-likelihood difference at
 95 a specific K_{eff} value is the sum of log-likelihood differences of sites of the specific
 96 K_{eff} value or lower. These figures are ideal for showing the preferred topology
 97 and for determining how decisive different K_{eff} -ranges are. Corresponding with
 98 Section Materials and Methods, a total log-likelihood difference above zero (blue
 99 area) means support for topology *B* and a total log-likelihood difference below zero
 100 (yellowish area) means support for the topology *A*.

101 *Site-proportional K_{eff} -axis.* – A modified version of the representation above
 102 can be seen in Figures S11 and S12 when the length of the x-axis is proportional
 103 to the number of sites observing the given K_{eff} value range.

104 *Different bin sizes.* – Figures S13, S14 and S15 show how the compositional
 105 constraint analysis changes for different bin sizes.

106 *Performance of CAT-PMSF compared to the PMSF method.* – The qual-
 107 ity of tree inference using amino acid site-specific stationary distributions esti-
 108 mated by the CAT-PMSF and PMSF methods were explored (Fig. S7, S8, S9, S10
 109 and S16). The exchangeabilities and discrete rate heterogeneity category numbers
 110 matched the ones used in previous steps (e.g. LG+PMSF was used for PhyloBayes
 111 LG+CAT).

112 *Settings for IQ-TREE 2 required to compare site-specific log-likelihoods of dif-*
 113 *ferent topologies.* – IQ-TREE 2 was set to output site-specific log-likelihood values
 114 (`-wslr`) and perform ultra-fast bootstrap (`-B 1000`). The output of site-specific

115 log-likelihood is necessary in order to create the “spectral analyses” but is unnece-
116 ssary if the sole aim is to infer a tree less prone to LBA.

117 *S3.1 Simulation study*

118 We simulated amino acid alignments with 10 000 sites exhibiting across-site com-
119 positional heterogeneity (Schrempf et al., 2020) along Felsenstein-type quartet
120 trees (insets in top row of Figure 2; Felsenstein, 1978) with different branch lengths
121 ($q = 0.1$ kept constant; $p = 0.1$ to $p = 2.0$ changed) under a site-heterogeneous
122 model with varying stationary distributions and constant Poisson (Felsenstein,
123 1973; Nei, 1987) exchangeabilities. We performed analyses with Poisson+CAT-
124 PMSF, LG+CAT-PMSF, GTR+CAT-PMSF, LG+C60 (Quang et al., 2008), LG+PMSF+C60 (Quang
125 et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2018), LG (Le and Gascuel, 2008), and GTR (Tavaré, 1986)
126 models constrained to the correct topology as well as the incorrect (Farris-type)
127 topology (inset in bottom row of Figure 2; Farris, 1999) with IQ-TREE 2 (Minh
128 et al., 2020). For Poisson+CAT-PMSF the effect of the guide topology used in Step
129 2 was explored, either setting the topology to the one inferred in Step 1 or to the
130 genuine one. A third run uses the genuine topology and site-specific amino acid
131 frequencies (*Poisson orig freq*). The site-specific log-likelihood differences $\Delta\log L$
132 between the maximum likelihood trees of the two competing topologies binned ac-
133 cording to their effective number of amino acids K_{eff} are shown in Figure S7. The
134 cumulative site-specific log-likelihood differences $\Delta\log L$ between the maximum like-
135 lihood trees of the two competing topologies as a function of the sites with increas-
136 ing effective number of amino acids K_{eff} estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and
137 Philippe, 2004) are shown in Figure S8. The LG, and GTR models incorrectly infer
138 Farris-type trees if $p \geq 0.8$. The exact log-likelihood differences of the competing
139 topologies are shown in Table S1 for Poisson+CAT-PMSF and in Table S2 for the
140 site-homogeneous LG model.

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Figure S7: **Compositional constraint analysis of the simulation study, binned representation.** Extended simulation study for all branch length combinations of p and q . The LG and GTR models incorrectly infer Farris-type trees if $p \geq 0.8$.

Figure S8: **Compositional constraint analysis of the simulation study, cumulative representation.** Cumulative log-likelihood differences for all branch length combinations of p and q . The LG and GTR models incorrectly infer Farris-type trees if $p \geq 0.8$.

Table S1: **Log-likelihood results of the simulation study, Poisson+CAT-PMSF model.**

q	p	$\log L_{\text{Farris}}$	$\log L_{\text{Felsenstein}}$	$\Delta \log L$
0.1	0.1	-23156.9	-22968.5	188.6
0.1	0.2	-33954.0	-33714.9	239.1
0.1	0.3	-39383.5	-39224.0	159.5
0.1	0.4	-42175.9	-42063.4	112.5
0.1	0.5	-44926.5	-44843.7	82.8
0.1	0.6	-46463.8	-46407.0	56.8
0.1	0.7	-48234.8	-48194.4	40.4
0.1	0.8	-49813.8	-49785.1	28.7
0.1	0.9	-50532.3	-50509.6	22.7
0.1	1.0	-51238.1	-51220.8	17.3
0.1	1.1	-52096.2	-52086.3	9.9
0.1	1.2	-52876.2	-52864.8	11.4
0.1	1.3	-53682.7	-53672.8	9.9
0.1	1.4	-54222.2	-54215.1	7.1
0.1	1.5	-54866.1	-54859.5	6.6
0.1	1.6	-54976.4	-54972.9	3.5
0.1	1.7	-55344.2	-55341.5	2.7
0.1	1.8	-55692.6	-55690.6	2.0
0.1	1.9	-55763.7	-55761.7	2.0
0.1	2.0	-56078.7	-56077.3	1.4

We simulated amino acid alignments with 10 000 sites exhibiting across-site compositional heterogeneity (Schrempf et al., 2020) along Felsenstein-type trees (insets in top row of Figure 2; Felsenstein, 1978) with different branch lengths ($q = 0.1$; $0.1 < p \leq 2.0$). Maximum log-likelihoods and log-likelihood differences of the competing topologies of the simulation dataset using the Poisson+CAT-PMSF model are shown. The true branch lengths p and q are indicated. A positive log-likelihood difference indicates support for the correct topology (Felsenstein-type), a negative difference for the incorrect (Farris-type) topology.

Table S2: **Log-likelihood results of the simulation study, LG model.**

q	p	$\log L_{\text{Farris}}$	$\log L_{\text{Felsenstein}}$	$\Delta \log L$
0.1	0.1	-53706.3	-52625.0	1081.3
0.1	0.2	-58628.7	-57949.5	679.2
0.1	0.3	-62163.4	-61769.0	394.4
0.1	0.4	-64806.2	-64557.0	249.2
0.1	0.5	-66744.9	-66579.6	165.3
0.1	0.6	-68552.4	-68468.5	83.9
0.1	0.7	-70075.2	-70053.8	21.4
0.1	0.8	-71390.2	-71427.6	-37.4
0.1	0.9	-72440.1	-72492.2	-52.1
0.1	1.0	-73454.8	-73540.1	-85.3
0.1	1.1	-74334.2	-74466.6	-132.4
0.1	1.2	-75057.2	-75202.9	-145.7
0.1	1.3	-75683.1	-75864.7	-181.6
0.1	1.4	-76326.1	-76525.7	-199.6
0.1	1.5	-76910.3	-77144.3	-234.0
0.1	1.6	-77480.0	-77743.8	-263.8
0.1	1.7	-77879.9	-78161.7	-281.8
0.1	1.8	-78269.3	-78576.8	-307.5
0.1	1.9	-78647.1	-78962.5	-315.4
0.1	2.0	-79045.8	-79378.8	-333.0

We simulated amino acid alignments with 10 000 sites exhibiting across-site compositional heterogeneity (Schrempf et al., 2020) along Felsenstein-type trees (insets in top row of Figure 2; Felsenstein, 1978) with different branch lengths ($q = 0.1$; $0.1 < p < 2.0$). Maximum log-likelihoods and log-likelihood differences of the competing topologies of the simulation dataset using the LG model are shown. The true branch lengths p and q are indicated. A positive log-likelihood difference indicates support for the correct topology (Felsenstein-type), a negative difference for the incorrect (Farris-type) topology.

141 *S3.2 Empirical datasets*

142 Here we show extended compositional constraint analysis figures with more mod-
 143 els and with cumulative log-likelihoods (Fig. S9 and S10), site-proportional K_{eff}
 144 (Fig. S11 and S12) or different bin sizes (Fig. S13, S14 and S15).

Figure S9: **Compositional constraint analysis of the empirical datasets, cumulative representation.** We analyzed three empirical datasets including (left) Platyhelminthes and (middle) Nematoda (Philippe et al., 2005), and (right) Microsporidia (Brinkmann et al., 2005). We performed analyses with LG+CAT-PMSF, GTR+CAT-PMSF, LG+C10 and LG+C60 (Quang et al., 2008), LG+C10+PMSF and LG+C60+PMSF (Quang et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2018), LG (Le and Gascuel, 2008) and GTR (Tavaré, 1986) models constrained to either one of two competing topologies with IQ-TREE 2 (Minh et al., 2020). The blue background indicates support for the topologies in Figures S3a, S1a and S2a; the yellowish background for the long branch attraction-prone topologies in Figures S3b, S1b and S2b. The cumulative log-likelihood differences $\Delta \log L$ between the LBA-prone and the non-LBA-prone topologies as a function of the sites with increasing effective number of amino acids K_{eff} estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) are shown. Site-homogeneous models infer the topology prone to long branch attraction for all three datasets. Conventional site-heterogeneous models infer the topology purportedly free of long branch attraction when enough categories are used. For the Platyhelminthes dataset 10 categories are not enough, but 60 are. For the Nematoda and Microsporidia datasets 10 categories are sufficient to model the across-site compositional heterogeneity in the data. We observe bias for the long branch attraction-prone topology for the low K_{eff} sites when using these methods, except for Microsporidia when using 60 categories. The CAT-PMSF method on the other hand is not showing correlations between K_{eff} value and topology preference.

Figure S10: **Compositional constraint analysis of Simion et al.'s reduced outgroup dataset, cumulative representation.** We performed analyses with Poisson+CAT-PMSF, LG+CAT-PMSF, GTR+CAT-PMSF, LG (Le and Gascuel, 2008), GTR (Tavaré, 1986), LG+C20+PMSF (Quang et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2018) and LG+C20 (Quang et al., 2008) models constrained to either one of two competing topologies (the blue background supports the topology in Figure S4a, the yellowish background the topology in Figure S4b) with IQ-TREE 2 (Minh et al., 2020). The cumulative site-specific log-likelihood differences $\Delta\log L$ between the maximum likelihood trees of the two competing topologies as a function of the sites with increasing effective number of amino acids K_{eff} estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) are shown. Site-homogeneous models and the site-heterogeneous LG+C20+PMSF and LG+C20 models show inconsistent signal between constrained versus unconstrained sites and favor Ctenophora at the animal root. CAT-PMSF favors Porifera at the animal root although this result is only significant when using the closest outgroup exclusively.

Figure S11: **Compositional constraint analysis of the empirical datasets, cumulative representation, with site-proportional K_{eff} .** Site-proportional version of S9 to visualise the number of sites within a given K_{eff} range.

Figure S12: **Compositional constraint analysis of *Simion et al.*'s reduced outgroup dataset, cumulative representation, with site-proportional K_{eff} .** Site-proportional version of S10 to visualise the number of sites within a given K_{eff} range.

Figure S13: Variation of compositional constraint analysis of the empirical datasets on Figure 3 with 10 bins.

Figure S14: Variation of compositional constraint analysis of the empirical datasets on Figure 3 with 5 bins.

Figure S15: Variation of compositional constraint analysis of the empirical datasets on Figure 3 with 4 bins.

145 S4 MEASURING CORRELATION BETWEEN K_{EFF} AND SITE-SPECIFIC LOG-LIKELIHOOD
146 DIFFERENCE

147 To assess the overall significance of the site-specific log-likelihood differences and
148 to evaluate whether site-homogeneous models are indeed biased, we calculated the
149 correlation between the log-likelihood difference and the effective number of used
150 amino acids K_{eff} per site. To this aim, the Pearson's correlation coefficient and
151 p-value were calculated for all datasets and models (Tables S3 and S4). Further,
152 the rank correlation coefficients of two nonparametric tests, the Spearman's rank
153 (Tables S6 and S5) and the Kendall's rank (Tables S8 and S7) were also calculated
154 using SciPy's libraries (Jones et al., 2001).

155 Overall, we observe: Invariant sites or sites with K_{eff} below 3 have low site-
156 specific log-likelihood differences especially for analyses based on CAT-PMSF. Thereby,
157 the rank correlation coefficients tend to be significant. If we remove sites with K_{eff}
158 below 3, the rank correlation coefficients are not anymore significant for analy-
159 ses based on CAT-PMSF (data not shown). Some sites with $3 < K_{\text{eff}} < 7$ show
160 high site-specific log-likelihood differences with classical models. They greatly in-
161 fluence the topology preference but not so much the rank correlation coefficients.
162 For these reasons, we think that correlation coefficients based on the site-specific
163 log-likelihood differences such as the Pearson's coefficient should be preferred over
164 correlation coefficients solely based on the rank.

Table S3: **Pearson's correlation test results for the simulation study.**

Dataset	Model	Pearson's r	p -value
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	0.021	0.032
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.012	0.246
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.016	0.121
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	0.018	0.079
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG	0.026	0.009
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	GTR	0.033	$9.553 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	0.013	0.179
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.043	$1.565 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.011	0.276
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	0.016	0.107
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG	0.051	$3.520 \cdot 10^{-7}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	GTR	0.045	$7.169 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	0.013	0.207
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.096	$9.348 \cdot 10^{-22}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.012	0.236
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	0.017	0.084
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG	0.072	$4.325 \cdot 10^{-13}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	GTR	0.053	$1.093 \cdot 10^{-7}$

Pearson's r and associated p -values for the correlation between the effective number of used amino acids K_{eff} per site and the site-specific log-likelihood difference between the two competing topologies. Values for the simulation study and models described in the main text are shown. Bold rows show significant correlation.

Table S4: Pearson's correlation test results for the empirical datasets.

Dataset	Model	Pearson's r	p -value
Platyhelminthes	LG+CAT-PMSF	-0.003	0.640
Platyhelminthes	GTR+CAT-PMSF	$1.135 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.998
Platyhelminthes	LG+PMSF+C60	0.024	$7.241 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Platyhelminthes	LG	0.028	$1.093 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Platyhelminthes	GTR	0.026	$1.015 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Nematoda	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.008	0.118
Nematoda	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.009	0.077
Nematoda	LG+PMSF+C60	0.025	$2.504 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Nematoda	LG	0.023	$1.234 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Nematoda	GTR	0.022	$2.514 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Microsporidia	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.011	0.099
Microsporidia	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.009	0.147
Microsporidia	LG+PMSF+C60	0.018	0.005
Microsporidia	LG	0.044	$5.931 \cdot 10^{-12}$
Microsporidia	GTR	0.040	$4.244 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.002	0.201
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR+CAT-PMSF	$3.079 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.845
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+PMSF+C20	0.014	$9.432 \cdot 10^{-20}$
Simion reduced outgroup	LG	0.008	$2.836 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR	0.007	$8.318 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Ryan	CAT-PMSF LG	-0.015	$1.024 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Ryan	CAT-PMSF GTR	-0.013	$1.696 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Ryan	LG+PMSF+C60	0.011	$8.659 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Ryan	LG	0.011	$1.070 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Ryan	GTR	0.010	$4.278 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Pearson's r and associated p -values for the correlation between the site-specific effective number of used amino acids K_{eff} as estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) and the site-specific log-likelihood difference between the two competing topologies. Results for the empirical datasets and models are shown. Bold rows show significant correlation.

Table S5: **Spearman's rank correlation test results for the simulation.**

Dataset	Model	Spearman's ρ	p -value
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	-0.005	0.602
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	-0.078	$4.754 \cdot 10^{-15}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.038	$1.220 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	-0.040	$6.921 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG	-0.048	$1.504 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	GTR	-0.018	0.073
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	-0.045	$5.996 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.075	$6.967 \cdot 10^{-14}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.046	$4.476 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	-0.010	0.304
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG	0.115	$1.605 \cdot 10^{-30}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	GTR	0.114	$4.547 \cdot 10^{-30}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	-0.038	$1.597 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.164	$1.531 \cdot 10^{-61}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.045	$6.292 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	-0.013	0.205
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG	0.147	$3.294 \cdot 10^{-49}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	GTR	0.138	$1.931 \cdot 10^{-43}$

Bold rows show non-significant correlations.

Table S6: **Spearman's rank correlation test results for the empirical datasets.**

Dataset	Model	Spearman's ρ	p -value
Platyhelminthes	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.016	0.002
Platyhelminthes	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.005	0.327
Platyhelminthes	LG+PMSF+C60	0.043	$3.605 \cdot 10^{-16}$
Platyhelminthes	LG	0.097	$1.654 \cdot 10^{-74}$
Platyhelminthes	GTR	0.089	$3.132 \cdot 10^{-63}$
Nematoda	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.035	$3.703 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Nematoda	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.025	$1.864 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Nematoda	LG+PMSF+C60	0.026	$7.573 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Nematoda	LG	0.028	$1.086 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Nematoda	GTR	0.029	$7.375 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Microsporidia	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.038	$2.261 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Microsporidia	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.017	0.008
Microsporidia	LG+PMSF+C60	0.038	$2.452 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Microsporidia	LG	0.144	$2.725 \cdot 10^{-113}$
Microsporidia	GTR	0.138	$5.984 \cdot 10^{-104}$
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.013	$2.802 \cdot 10^{-16}$
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.072	0.0
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+PMSF+C20	0.006	$3.481 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Simion reduced outgroup	LG	0.008	$9.191 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR	0.043	$7.189 \cdot 10^{-164}$
Ryan	LG+CAT-PMSF	-0.116	$2.180 \cdot 10^{-260}$
Ryan	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.068	$9.809 \cdot 10^{-90}$
Ryan	LG+PMSF+C60	0.115	$1.352 \cdot 10^{-255}$
Ryan	LG	0.111	$1.763 \cdot 10^{-239}$
Ryan	GTR	0.105	$1.414 \cdot 10^{-213}$

Bold rows show non-significant correlation.

Table S7: **Kendall's rank correlation test results for the simulation.**

Dataset	Model	Kendall's τ	p -value
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	-0.004	0.600
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	-0.053	$3.964 \cdot 10^{-15}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.026	$1.045 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	-0.027	$6.627 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	LG	-0.032	$1.665 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 0.2, q = 0.1$	GTR	-0.012	0.071
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	-0.031	$4.956 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.051	$1.934 \cdot 10^{-14}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.031	$4.828 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	-0.007	0.281
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	LG	0.078	$6.343 \cdot 10^{-31}$
$p = 0.8, q = 0.1$	GTR	0.077	$1.104 \cdot 10^{-30}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	Poisson+CAT-PMSF	-0.026	$9.349 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.112	$9.416 \cdot 10^{-63}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.031	$4.741 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG+PMSF+C60	-0.009	0.183
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	LG	0.099	$1.062 \cdot 10^{-49}$
$p = 1.2, q = 0.1$	GTR	0.093	$3.651 \cdot 10^{-44}$

Bold rows show non-significant correlation.

Table S8: **Kendall's rank correlation test results for the empirical datasets.**

Dataset	Model	Kendall's τ	p -value
Platyhelminthes	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.019	$9.877 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Platyhelminthes	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.010	0.004
Platyhelminthes	LG+PMSF+C60	0.027	$1.183 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Platyhelminthes	LG	0.064	$6.404 \cdot 10^{-73}$
Platyhelminthes	GTR	0.061	$1.148 \cdot 10^{-66}$
Nematoda	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.047	$3.472 \cdot 10^{-40}$
Nematoda	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.039	$2.030 \cdot 10^{-28}$
Nematoda	LG+PMSF+C60	0.001	0.687
Nematoda	LG	0.005	0.184
Nematoda	GTR	$1.770 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.960
Microsporidia	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.035	$4.865 \cdot 10^{-16}$
Microsporidia	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.018	$2.427 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Microsporidia	LG+PMSF+C60	0.024	$1.592 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Microsporidia	LG	0.090	$3.567 \cdot 10^{-98}$
Microsporidia	GTR	0.087	$8.006 \cdot 10^{-91}$
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+CAT-PMSF	0.018	$2.376 \cdot 10^{-60}$
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR+CAT-PMSF	0.074	0.0
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+PMSF+C20	-0.028	$1.118 \cdot 10^{-157}$
Simion reduced outgroup	LG	-0.029	$2.112 \cdot 10^{-165}$
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR	0.009	$2.045 \cdot 10^{-16}$
Ryan	LG+CAT-PMSF	-0.080	$4.908 \cdot 10^{-256}$
Ryan	GTR+CAT-PMSF	-0.047	$3.986 \cdot 10^{-83}$
Ryan	LG+PMSF+C60	0.064	$2.730 \cdot 10^{-176}$
Ryan	LG	0.053	$2.898 \cdot 10^{-124}$
Ryan	GTR	0.049	$1.198 \cdot 10^{-106}$

Bold rows show non-significant correlation.

169 Approximately Unbiased tests (AU, Shimodaira, 2002) were run on the maximum
170 likelihood trees constrained to the topologies inferred at Step 1 and Step 3 of the
171 CAT-PMSF method. As shown in Tables S12, S13, S14 and S15 the topology
172 inferred at Step 3 (T1) is significantly more probable under the model than the
173 LBA-prone topology of Step 1 (T2). This is in accordance with the results presented
174 by the compositional constraint analysis.

Table S9: AU test results for the simulation study with GTR+CAT-PMSF model.

q	p	p-AU _{T1}		p-AU _{T2}	
0.1	0.1	1	+	$1.87 \cdot 10^{-8}$	-
0.1	0.2	1	+	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-58}$	-
0.1	0.3	1	+	$6.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-
0.1	0.4	1	+	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-49}$	-
0.1	0.5	1	+	$2.87 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-
0.1	0.6	1	+	$6.03 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-
0.1	0.7	1	+	$1.89 \cdot 10^{-7}$	-
0.1	0.8	1	+	$2.31 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-
0.1	0.9	1	+	$1.98 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-
0.1	1.0	0.998	+	$1.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
0.1	1.1	0.993	+	$6.60 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
0.1	1.2	0.996	+	$3.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
0.1	1.3	0.99	+	$9.78 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
0.1	1.4	0.964	+	$3.56 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
0.1	1.5	0.918	+	$8.17 \cdot 10^{-2}$	+
0.1	1.6	0.321	+	0.679	+
0.1	1.7	0.54	+	0.46	+
0.1	1.8	0.161	+	0.839	+
0.1	1.9	0.377	+	0.623	+
0.1	2.0	0.237	+	0.763	+

The T1 topology constraint is the same as the ML topology output by the CAT-PMSF pipeline, whereas the T2 topology constraint is the ML topology under the specified model with a constraint producing the long branch attraction artifact. Minus signs mean significant exclusion of the topology, plus signs mean that the topology could not be excluded within the 95% confidence interval.

Table S10: AU test results for the simulation study with LG+CAT-PMSF model.

q	p	p-AU _{T1}		p-AU _{T2}	
0.1	0.1	1	+	$3.06 \cdot 10^{-51}$	-
0.1	0.2	1	+	$4.37 \cdot 10^{-48}$	-
0.1	0.3	1	+	$3.98 \cdot 10^{-38}$	-
0.1	0.4	1	+	$1.78 \cdot 10^{-50}$	-
0.1	0.5	1	+	$7.64 \cdot 10^{-7}$	-
0.1	0.6	1	+	$2.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-
0.1	0.7	0.998	+	$2.34 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
0.1	0.8	0.912	+	$8.76 \cdot 10^{-2}$	+
0.1	0.9	0.795	+	0.205	+
0.1	1.0	0.255	+	0.745	+
0.1	1.1	$3.39 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	0.997	+
0.1	1.2	$5.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	0.999	+
0.1	1.3	$3.87 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	1	+
0.1	1.4	$2.26 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-	1	+
0.1	1.5	$4.95 \cdot 10^{-11}$	-	1	+
0.1	1.6	$6.79 \cdot 10^{-51}$	-	1	+
0.1	1.7	$2.11 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	1	+
0.1	1.8	$5.46 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	0.999	+
0.1	1.9	$7.35 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	0.999	+
0.1	2.0	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-10}$	-	1	+

The T1 topology constraint is the same as the ML topology output by the CAT-PMSF pipeline, whereas the T2 topology constraint is the ML topology under the specified model with a constraint producing the long branch attraction artifact. Minus signs mean significant exclusion of the topology, plus signs mean that the topology could not be excluded within the 95% confidence interval.

Table S11: AU test results for the simulation study with Poisson+CAT-PMSF model.

q	p	p-AU _{T1}		p-AU _{T2}	
0.1	0.1	1	+	$1.82 \cdot 10^{-8}$	-
0.1	0.2	1	+	$2.57 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-
0.1	0.3	1	+	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-
0.1	0.4	1	+	$2.59 \cdot 10^{-65}$	-
0.1	0.5	1	+	$1.37 \cdot 10^{-62}$	-
0.1	0.6	1	+	$2.09 \cdot 10^{-9}$	-
0.1	0.7	1	+	$2.29 \cdot 10^{-9}$	-
0.1	0.8	1	+	$1.46 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-
0.1	0.9	0.999	+	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
0.1	1.0	0.997	+	$3.15 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
0.1	1.1	0.984	+	$1.61 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
0.1	1.2	0.989	+	$1.07 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
0.1	1.3	0.982	+	$1.84 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
0.1	1.4	0.968	+	$3.17 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
0.1	1.5	0.957	+	$4.27 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
0.1	1.6	0.898	+	0.102	+
0.1	1.7	0.875	+	0.125	+
0.1	1.8	0.835	+	0.165	+
0.1	1.9	0.836	+	0.164	+
0.1	2.0	0.786	+	0.214	+

The T1 topology constraint is the same as the ML topology output by the CAT-PMSF pipeline, whereas the T2 topology constraint is the ML topology under the specified model with a constraint producing the long branch attraction artifact. Minus signs mean significant exclusion of the topology, plus signs mean that the topology could not be excluded within the 95% confidence interval.

Table S12: **AU test results for the Microsporidia dataset with CAT-PMSF models.**

Model	p-AU _{T1}		p-AU _{T2}	
LG+CAT-PMSF, chain 1	1	+	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$	–
LG+CAT-PMSF, chain 2	1	+	$1.69 \cdot 10^{-7}$	–
GTR+CAT-PMSF, chain 1	1	+	$1.25 \cdot 10^{-49}$	–
GTR+CAT-PMSF, chain 2	1	+	$3.27 \cdot 10^{-74}$	–

The T1 topology constraint is the same as the ML topology output by the CAT-PMSF pipeline, whereas the T2 topology constraint is the ML topology under the specified model with a constraint producing the long branch attraction artifact. Minus signs mean significant exclusion of the topology, plus signs mean that the topology could not be excluded within the 95% confidence interval.

Table S13: **AU test results for the Nematoda dataset with CAT-PMSF models.**

Model	p-AU _{T1}		p-AU _{T2}	
LG+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.484	+	$7.18 \cdot 10^{-8}$	–
LG+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.51	+	$2.02 \cdot 10^{-71}$	–
GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.491	+	$1.01 \cdot 10^{-10}$	–
GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.503	+	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-83}$	–

T1 tree constraint is the same topology as the ML tree outputted by the CAT-PMSF pipeline, whereas T2 tree constraint is the ML tree under the specified model with a constraint producing the long branch attraction artifact. Minus signs mean significant exclusion of the topology, plus signs mean that the topology could not be excluded within the 95% confidence interval.

Table S14: **AU test results for the *Platyhelminthes* dataset with CAT-PMSF models.**

Model	p-AU _{T1}		p-AU _{T2}	
LG+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.485	+	$2.05 \cdot 10^{-6}$	–
LG+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.493	+	$3.65 \cdot 10^{-5}$	–
GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.497	+	$7.44 \cdot 10^{-6}$	–
GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.493	+	$8.26 \cdot 10^{-3}$	–

T1 tree constraint is the same topology as the ML tree outputted by the CAT-PMSF pipeline, whereas T2 tree constraint is the ML tree under the specified model with a constraint producing the long branch attraction artifact. Minus signs mean significant exclusion of the topology, plus signs mean that the topology could not be excluded within the 95% confidence interval.

Table S15: **AU test results for the *Simion et al.* dataset with reduced and all the outgroups using CAT-PMSF models.**

Dataset	Model	p-AU _{T1}		p-AU _{T2}	
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.606	+	$7.73 \cdot 10^{-4}$	–
Simion reduced outgroup	LG+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.605	+	$4.42 \cdot 10^{-4}$	–
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.517	+	$6.61 \cdot 10^{-4}$	–
Simion reduced outgroup	GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.502	+	$3.11 \cdot 10^{-4}$	–
Simion all outgroups	LG+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.604	+	0.396	+
Simion all outgroups	LG+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.587	+	0.413	+
Simion all outgroups	GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 1	0.96	+	$4.04 \cdot 10^{-2}$	–
Simion all outgroups	GTR+CAT-PMSF chain 2	0.96	+	$3.97 \cdot 10^{-2}$	–

T1 tree constraint is the same topology as the ML tree outputted by the CAT-PMSF pipeline, whereas T2 tree constraint is the ML tree under the specified model with a constraint producing the long branch attraction artifact. Minus signs mean significant exclusion of the topology, plus signs mean that the topology could not be excluded within the 95% confidence interval.

175 S6 FILTERING OUT DISTANT OUTGROUPS HELPS REDUCE LONG BRANCH AT-
 176 TRACTION

177 AU tests (Table S15) for the full Simion dataset (including 7 further outgroup
 178 species) could not reject the Ctenophora topology for LG+CAT-PMSF and barely
 179 rejected it for GTR+CAT-PMSF. This behavior is shown on the compositional
 180 constraint analysis (Fig. S16) where the CAT-PMSF results were not consistent,
 181 resembling the features of site-homogeneous and not complex enough site-hetero-
 182 geneous models. Keeping only the closest outgroup, Choanoflagellata (Fig. 4,
 183 S10 and S12), the AU test rejects the Ctenophora-sister topology (Table S15) and
 184 the CAT-PMSF model provides a weak, but consistent signal towards the Porifera-
 185 sister topology, which — based on the other cases presented in the main text — may
 186 imply that the Porifera-sister topology is the more probable animal root according
 187 to this dataset.

Figure S16: **Compositional constraint analysis of Simion et al.’s full out-group dataset, binned and cumulative representation.** We performed analyses with the LG+CAT-PMSF, GTR+CAT-PMSF, LG (Le and Gascuel, 2008) and GTR (Tavaré, 1986) models constrained to either one of two competing topologies (the blue background supports the topology in Figure S5a, the yellowish background the topology in Figure S5b) with IQ-TREE 2 (Minh et al., 2020). On the left side the site-specific log-likelihood differences $\Delta\log L$ between the maximum likelihood trees of the two competing topologies binned according to their effective number of amino acids K_{eff} estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) are shown. On the right side the cumulative site-specific log-likelihood differences $\Delta\log L$ between the maximum likelihood trees of the two competing topologies as a function of the sites with increasing effective number of amino acids K_{eff} estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) are shown. Site-homogeneous models strongly favor Ctenophora at the animal root. LG+CAT-PMSF favors Ctenophora, while GTR+CAT-PMSF Porifera at the animal root, their signal is inconsistent.

188 S7 RESULTS FOR ANOTHER METAZOA DATASET

189 We investigated a second dataset (Ryan et al., 2013) covering Metazoa. The results
 190 of the CAT-PMSF method suggest there is hardly any signal in the alignment
 191 discriminating between the two topologies (Fig. S17).

Figure S17: **Compositional constraint analysis of the Ryan et al. dataset, binned and cumulative representation.** We performed analyses with the LG+CAT-PMSF, GTR+CAT-PMSF, LG (Le and Gascuel, 2008), GTR (Tavaré, 1986) and LG+C60+PMSF (Quang et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2018) models constrained to either one of two competing topologies (the blue background supports the topology in Figure S6a, the yellowish background the topology in Figure S6b) with IQ-TREE 2 (Minh et al., 2020). On the left side the site-specific log-likelihood differences $\Delta\log L$ between the maximum likelihood trees of the two competing topologies binned according to their effective number of amino acids K_{eff} estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) are shown. On the right side the cumulative site-specific log-likelihood differences $\Delta\log L$ between the maximum likelihood trees of the two competing topologies as a function of the sites with increasing effective number of amino acids K_{eff} estimated by PhyloBayes (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) are shown. Site-homogeneous models and the site-heterogeneous LG+C60+PMSF models show favor Ctenophora at the animal root. CAT-PMSF does not provide significant support to either of the topologies, there is not enough signal in the dataset.

192 S8 COMPOSITIONAL HETEROGENEITY ACROSS SEQUENCES

193 CAT-PMSF assumes homogeneity of the evolutionary process across the branches
 194 of the tree. The software Homo v2.1 <https://github.com/ljsjermin/Homo.v2.1>
 195 tests for compositional heterogeneity between sequences of an alignment. The simu-
 196 lated alignments do not show any signs of compositional heterogeneity between the
 197 sequences (for detailed results, see in the Dryad Digital Repository: [https://doi.](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g79cnp5rh)
 198 [org/10.5061/dryad.g79cnp5rh](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g79cnp5rh) and at <https://github.com/drenal/cat-pmsf-paper>).
 199 As expected, empirical alignments exhibit some level of compositional heterogene-
 200 ity across branches. The following listings show the output of Homo v2.1 for the
 201 empirical datasets used in this study.

202 We observed that the significance of the test depends on the length of the
 203 sequences. In particular, we observed longer sequences reject compositional homo-
 204 geneity with more significant p-values than shorter sequences (for detailed results,
 205 please see in the Dryad Digital Repository: [https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g79cnp5rh)
 206 [g79cnp5rh](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.g79cnp5rh) and at <https://github.com/drenal/cat-pmsf-paper>). For example,
 207 the metazoan dataset of Ryan et al. (2013) has only 88k sites compared to approx-
 208 imately 400k sites of the metazoan dataset of Simion et al. (2017).

```

1   Positions in alignment ..... 24294
2   Number of tests ..... 780
3   Smallest P value ..... 2.400863e-256
4   Level of significance (tau) ..... 0.050000
5   Proportion of P values below tau ..... 0.778205
6   Tests rejected (Bonferroni 1936) ..... 426
7   Tests rejected (Holm 1979) ..... 434
8   Tests rejected (Benjamini & Yekutieli 2001) .. 514
9   Min(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.006442
10  Max(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.021476
11  Min(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.002527
12  Max(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.023086
13  Min(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.003250
14  Max(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.069037
15  Min(p distance) ..... 0.094614
16  Max(p distance) ..... 0.603223
    
```

Listing S1: Results of Homo v2.1 for the dataset including Microsporidia.

CONSTRAINED SITES DRIVE LONG BRANCH ATTRACTION S.MAT.

```
1 Positions in alignment ..... 35371
2 Number of tests ..... 666
3 Smallest P value ..... 1.002749e-37
4 Level of significance (tau) ..... 0.050000
5 Proportion of P values below tau ..... 0.681682
6 Tests rejected (Bonferroni 1936) ..... 300
7 Tests rejected (Holm 1979) ..... 309
8 Tests rejected (Benjamini & Yekutieli 2001) .. 370
9 Min(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.005438
10 Max(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.018051
11 Min(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.000995
12 Max(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.011907
13 Min(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.000941
14 Max(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.025573
15 Min(p distance) ..... 0.029410
16 Max(p distance) ..... 0.398590
```

Listing S2: Results of Homo v2.1 for the dataset including Nematoda.

```
1 Positions in alignment ..... 35371
2 Number of tests ..... 496
3 Smallest P value ..... 1.139181e-38
4 Level of significance (tau) ..... 0.050000
5 Proportion of P values below tau ..... 0.675403
6 Tests rejected (Bonferroni 1936) ..... 232
7 Tests rejected (Holm 1979) ..... 239
8 Tests rejected (Benjamini & Yekutieli 2001) .. 283
9 Min(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.005438
10 Max(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.020186
11 Min(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.001709
12 Max(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.015175
13 Min(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.002571
14 Max(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.032438
15 Min(p distance) ..... 0.047276
16 Max(p distance) ..... 0.409459
```

Listing S3: Results of Homo v2.1 for the dataset including Platyhelminthes.

```
1 Positions in alignment ..... 401632
2 Number of tests ..... 4656
3 Smallest P value ..... 0.000000e+00
4 Level of significance (tau) ..... 0.050000
5 Proportion of P values below tau ..... 0.987328
6 Tests rejected (Bonferroni 1936) ..... 4387
7 Tests rejected (Holm 1979) ..... 4470
8 Tests rejected (Benjamini & Yekutieli 2001) .. 4537
9 Min(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.001975
10 Max(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.012568
11 Min(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.000498
12 Max(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.015231
13 Min(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.000839
14 Max(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.042335
15 Min(p distance) ..... 0.047812
16 Max(p distance) ..... 0.441469
```

Listing S4: Results of Homo v2.1 for the metazoan dataset of [Simion et al. \(2017\)](#).

```
1 Positions in alignment ..... 88384
2 Number of tests ..... 1830
3 Smallest P value ..... 6.090868e-255
4 Level of significance (tau) ..... 0.050000
5 Proportion of P values below tau ..... 0.362295
6 Tests rejected (Bonferroni 1936) ..... 289
7 Tests rejected (Holm 1979) ..... 289
8 Tests rejected (Benjamini & Yekutieli 2001) .. 392
9 Min(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.000000
10 Max(delta_Bowker) ..... 0.126419
11 Min(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.001647
12 Max(delta_EuclideanFS) ..... 0.071180
13 Min(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.002744
14 Max(delta_EuclideanMS) ..... 0.117840
15 Min(p distance) ..... 0.059097
16 Max(p distance) ..... 0.544691
```

Listing S5: Results of Homo v2.1 for the metazoan dataset of [Ryan et al. \(2013\)](#).

210 Here we show the output of Phylobayes' (Lartillot and Philippe, 2004) tool `tracecomp`
 211 to assess the convergence between the two Markov chains started for each align-
 212 ment.

Table S16: Convergence of Phylobayes LG+CAT+G4 analyses for the Microsporidia dataset

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	594	0.0929612
length	596	0.0690003
alpha	231	0.129453
Nmode	623	0.0078885
statent	303	0.111053
statalpha	520	0.0183449

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 4000.

Table S17: Convergence of Phylobayes GTR+CAT+G4 analyses for the Microsporidia dataset

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	766	0.0619622
length	180	0.171073
alpha	143	0.233501
Nmode	345	0.0253067
statent	242	0.0190515
statalpha	145	0.131871
rrent	282	0.0766182
rrmean	4773	0.00114388

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S18: **Convergence of Phylobayes LG+CAT+G4 analyses for the Nematoda dataset**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	515	0.0539381
length	1296	0.0732629
alpha	798	0.0325119
Nmode	823	0.000358915
statent	719	0.0628802
statalpha	316	0.0598403

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S19: **Convergence of Phylobayes GTR+CAT+G4 analyses for the Nematoda dataset**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	540	0.15339
length	5339	0.250924
alpha	4724	0.182099
Nmode	1292	0.0321017
statent	301	0.00237055
statalpha	419	0.180082
rrent	342	0.130712
rrmean	6179	0.00141907

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S20: **Convergence of Phylobayes LG+CAT+G4 analyses for the Platyhelminthes dataset**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	110	0.0514937
length	634	0.04558
alpha	568	0.0253402
Nmode	3691	0.0366779
statent	137	0.0540562
statalpha	166	0.0345426

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S21: **Convergence of Phylobayes GTR+CAT+G4 analyses for the Platyhelminthes dataset**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	359	0.351519
length	418	0.0778552
alpha	401	0.43393
Nmode	347	0.0557145
statent	381	0.262808
statalpha	430	0.102403
rrent	2906	0.117868
rrmean	7249	0.0108546

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S22: **Convergence of Phylobayes LG+CAT+G4 analyses for the Simion et al. dataset with Choanoflagellata as outgroup**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	147	0.381065
length	41	0.129443
alpha	151	0.323356
Nmode	218	0.107418
statent	139	0.180409
statalpha	72	0.0778117

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S23: **Convergence of Phylobayes GTR+CAT+G4 analyses for the Simion et al. dataset with Choanoflagellata as outgroup**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	159	0.480894
length	107	1.19047
alpha	87	1.94857
Nmode	115	0.168816
statent	111	3.54829
statalpha	48	0.370279
rrent	136	0.734394
rrmean	2461	0.0347738

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S24: **Convergence of Phylobayes Poisson+CAT+G4 analyses for the Simion et al. dataset with Choanoflagellata as outgroup**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	142	0.0572755
length	1009	0.0122319
alpha	661	0.0971534
Nmode	118	0.106781
statent	282	0.0674665
statalpha	172	0.0401437

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 3000.

Table S25: **Convergence of Phylobayes LG+CAT+G4 analyses for the Simion et al. dataset including distant outgroups**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	199	0.0207354
length	478	0.000169223
alpha	559	0.0570139
Nmode	333	0.0671745
statent	591	0.0899417
statalpha	117	0.151863

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S26: **Convergence of Phylobayes GTR+CAT+G4 analyses for the Simion et al. dataset including distant outgroups**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	33	1.92869
length	261	0.124522
alpha	94	2.27226
Nmode	179	0.22674
statent	74	2.6127
statalpha	204	0.0657509
rrent	205	0.339186
rrmean	4999	0.003295

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 1000.

Table S27: **Convergence of Phylobayes LG+CAT+G4 analyses for the Ryan et al. dataset**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	313	0.0435181
length	227	0.0927871
alpha	167	0.052443
Nmode	327	0.00677682
statent	297	0.0662057
statalpha	274	0.0772407

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for `tracecomp` was set to 3000.

Table S28: **Convergence of Phylobayes GTR+CAT+G4 analyses for the Ryan et al. dataset**

Parameter	Effective sample size	Relative difference
loglik	294	0.176161
length	626	0.0480805
alpha	292	0.0418603
Nmode	681	0.225009
statent	136	0.176489
statalpha	64	0.0754489
rrent	265	0.025304
rrmean	2861	0.0100864

Two Markov chains were run, burnin for tracecomp was set to 2700.

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